

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING STUDENTS

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Relevance: The modern methods of the educational process aimed at the comprehensive computerization and visualization of teaching subjects are focused on enhancing the quality of professional skills development in students. The effectiveness of the taught material is directly related not only to digital technologies but also to the preparedness of each specific teacher, their moral qualities, ability to engage students, and to involve them in research activities and extracurricular work.

Goal: To implement interactive teaching forms with the aim of improving the training of students in medical sciences.

Methods and Techniques: The educational process based on the use of interactive teaching methods is organized in such a way as to engage all students in the learning process without exception. Collaborative activity implies that each individual contributes their unique perspective and involves the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and methods of activity during the work process. Individual, pair, and group work is organized, along with project work and the use of role-playing games, as well as working with documents and various information sources. Interactive methods are based on mutual interaction, student activity, reliance on group experience, and principles of mandatory feedback. The introduction of computer technologies into the educational process such as online conferences, slide presentations, computer modeling, and other existing teaching methods has also proven effective according to research. The ability to discuss problems arising in telecommunications with the teacher informally and quickly, to organize discussions, and to present various theoretical materials in electronic form is crucial. The implementation of distance education generally does not significantly affect the spatial and temporal positioning of the teacher and student; a new educational information environment is created, allowing students to better understand which knowledge, skills, and abilities are more suitable. At the same time, the teacher must consider that text dialogues in social networks require careful and well-thought-out responses, as they contribute to mutual knowledge formation through broader communication and have educational prospects since growth in individual academic performance is noted. However, regardless of how dominant new educational directions may be, lectures have remained and will continue to be the most important form of teaching. Today, lectures have a "digital" format that enhances the presentation of the material.

Results: Students are increasingly choosing new methods of recording information—using laptops, which provide access to numerous textbooks and sometimes direct access to the Internet. There are more portals where students can exchange their work: created presentations, digital laboratory journals. Digital educational resources are increasing. Computer programs installed on smartphones allow for quick access to necessary information without using paper sources. High-quality communicators with built-in cameras enable capturing complex diagrams and opening various applications, including complete anatomical atlases.

Conclusions: Interactive forms of education help students understand and retain learned material more easily by actively participating in the educational process. Interactive teaching methods

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are directly related to the personal information of the teacher, maintaining the principle of individual approach to each student. Furthermore, the increasing proximity of students to the teacher necessitates self-improvement to have skills in using information technologies at the level of students, keeping pace with the times.